

The Politico-Ideological Rivalry of Iran and Saudi Arabia Post Islamic Revolution: Impacts on Pakistan

Abdul Rab, Mansoor Ahmed, Muhammad Ramzan, Amir Jan, Mobeen Ahmed, Sana Ullah

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 05, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Ideological Conflict, Extremism, Foreign Policy, Pakistan, Middle East, Iran, Saudi Arabi</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5984959</p>	<p><i>The paper highlights the politico-ideological differences of Iran and Saudi Arabia and impacts on Pakistan. The outbreak of Islamic Revolution, accelerated the ideological differences between Iran and Saudi Arabia in the region whose impacts were felt on the region particularly and on Pakistan specifically since Pakistan has religious, political and economic linkages with both of the states. Thus, the situation always remain tense for Pakistan to remain neutral between Iran and and Saudi conflict. The paper found that Pakistan has always tried to create balanced relationship between Iran and Saudi since both states are equally important for Pakistan in term of economy and politics. In order to identify the possible impacts of Iran and Saudi rivalry on Pakistan, this paper addresses the question, how Pakistan can escape from the impact while maintaining a balanced relationship between them? The paper is qualitative in nature and based on analysis, description and investigation of the historical facts, incidents and events which took place between Iran and Saudi Arabia.</i></p>

Introduction

Middle East which is located at the juncture of Eurasia, Africa, Mediterranean and Red Sea, is bestowed with different sort of natural and mineral resources. Despite its richness in oil, gas and other mineral resources, Middle East has been the center of politico-religious conflicts since the political division of the area in 1948. The political engineering of Middle East promoted religious extremism, political instability, social defragmentation and economic recession in the area whose impacts are felt worldwide. In addition to this, the regional and international players have been active in the region to enhance their respective sphere of influences in Middle East. Thus, these major regional and international powers have successfully divided the states of Middle East into two opposite camps on religious grounds. Sadly, the ideological conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia has not only accelerated extremism, and enhanced sectarianism in the region, it has created enough space for the non-state actors to strengthen their roots (Zaman, 2015). Horrendously, the implications of religious extremism and ideological conflict of Middle East have gradually engulfed the Muslim states including Pakistan. Despite the fact that Pakistan, having no geographical link with the states of Middle East, has been the first Muslim state to receive the direct implications of the politico-religious conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia due to its economic, religious and political links with Iran and Saudi Arabia. Moreover, Pakistan cannot afford to isolate itself from Saudi Arabia and Iran due to economic, religious and political links. Therefore, while formulating the foreign policy in respect to Iran and Saudi Arabia, Pakistan finds it tough to have a neutral stance over the politico-religious conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia. No doubt, Pakistan has strongly maintained that Pakistan would neither be the part of any religious conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia, nor it would entertain their respective interest or call. It would rather play a mediatory role in the conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia.

Significance of the Study

The nature of Pak-Iran-Saudi triangle is an extremely complicated one since Iran and Saudi Arabia have been observed in ideological conflict since 1979 in Middle East. Moreover, since 1979, Iran has been active in promoting Shiaism in regional Muslim states which has been greatly opposed and countered by Saudi Arabia. The enhancement of activities of GCC in the region, the establishment of Pak-US strategic partnership in 1980s were considered were not in favor of Iran. What hurt Iran the most was the inclination of Pakistan towards Saudi Arabia and US in the decade of 1980. Meanwhile, the newly Shia Regime faced a bloody war with Iraq (1980-88) which further tested Pak-Iran relations.

Apart from the historical Pak-Saudi-US cooperation, Pakistan has also maintained good relations with Iran. No doubt, Pakistan hosts a great number of Shia sect who have close links with Iran. Considering the geographical proximity, geo-politico-economic necessities of their bilateral relations and socio-cultural affiliation of people to people of Iran and Pakistan, the relations of both states are worth exploring in order to

forward certain policy options to strengthen their relations. Therefore, this study is extremely important to find out the implications of the ideological conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia on Pakistan.

Historical Perspective the Study

Middle East, being a strategically important region, has attracted the regional powers to ensure their presence for their respective regional sphere of influence. As a result, the foreign interference and politico-religious conflict of Middle East converted the region into a warzone region. In order to further widen the gap between the Muslim states of the Middle East, different non-state-entities have been given birth in the said region. Islamic States of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) Al-Nusra Front, Al-Qaida, Sunni-Shia differences and many more conflicts have been created to tensionize the region. Moreover, their presence made enough excuses for US and its allies to intervene in Middle East. Saudi Arabia which is an oil-rich country, has a tremendous share in supplying oil throughout the world, has close link with the US and Pakistan, whereas Iran-Saudi relations have been extremely hot since both states are viewed as traditional rivals and arch enemies of one another due to their ideological difference (Tadjbakhsh, 2013). Thus, their bitter relations and ideological differences resulted the birth of many non-state entities which have become the main cause of political disturbance of Middle East.

On the other hand, it must be kept in mind that Pakistan cannot afford to lose its relations with Iran which is not only a neighbor state, but also helped Pakistan politically, socially and economically. Iran was the first country which recognized Pakistan and supported Pakistan's independence on international platforms. Iran helped Pakistan in the difficult hours especially in wars of 1965 and 1971 against India (Alam, 2004). Therefore, Pakistan wants to maintain cordial relations with Iran. However, it has been very difficult for Pakistan to keep a balanced relationship between Iran and Saudi Arabia because it is the core objective of Saudi Arab's foreign policy to curtail Iranian policy (Elad-Altman, 2007) in order to curtail the role of Iran in Muslim states in Middle East. It is generally believed that before the ideology of Shiaism spreads in the Muslim world, Saudi Arabia aim to counter Shiaism (Kalin & Siddiqui, 2014) whereas Iran has been seen in enhancing and promoting its ideology in Syria, Iraq and other regional states in order to balance the power with Saudi Arabia and Israel (Cooper, 2012). Iran, being a Shia-dominated state, has been extremely rigid to acquire uranium enrichment by any means. No doubt, the international community targeted Iran with heavy economic sanctions and political isolation to force Iran to abandon the nuclear path; however, Iran has maintained that it would acquire uranium enrichment for peaceful purposes (Nikou, 2015). The rigidity and inflexibility of Iran made Iran isolated politically and crunched its economically. Therefore, in this hard time, Iran extremely needed the help of Pakistan to support Iran.

It has been reported that Iran and Saudi Arabia both have backed and supported their ideological groups in the region. Iran has been seen in helping Shias in the region whereas Saudi Arabia has supported the Sunni sect to counter the Shia-related-policy of Iran (Moonis, 2008). Thus, the race has given birth to extremist activities in the region. It also should be noted that the ideological war of Iran and Saudi affected Pakistan.

It is said that in the conflict of US-Saudi-Iran triangle, Pakistan could neither neutralize its relations with Saudi Arabia and Iran nor strengthen its ties with the said states equally. The government of Saudi Arabia and US have not been pleased with Pak-Iranian relations. (Mazhar & Goraya, 2013). For instance; contrary the fact that Pakistan extremely required energy in order to suffice its energy needs. But regrettably to state that both, the governments of Saudi Arabia and US opposed Iran-Pakistan (IP) Gas pipeline (Mazhar & Goraya, 2013).

However, the establishment of Pak-US strategic partnership in 1980s disturbed Pak-Iran relations badly. Meanwhile Pakistan soft corner with the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) further widened the gulf between Pak-Iran relations (Rizvi, 1982) (Pande, 2011). Despite having extremely close ties with Saudi Arabia, Pakistan did not oppose Shia school at any stage. Nonetheless, it even condemned and raised objection over the killing of Shia Pilgrims in Mecca in 1987 (Shah, 1997). However, Pakistan's link with GCC was criticized by Iran.

The same period also witnessed the deterioration of Pak-Iran relations over the establishment of Pak-US strategic partnership in the eve of Soviet intervention in Afghanistan since Iran believed that Pak-US strategic partnership was meant to equip and train the Afghan fled Mujahedeen for the retreat of Soviet forces from Afghanistan, would be ultimately used against Iran (Chossudovsky, 2001). Furthermore, Iran further alleged US for exploiting the Mujahedeen factor against the Shia Community in order to encounter the expansion of Shite policy beyond Iran's border (Emadi, 1995). In this dirty game, the Central Investigation Agency (CIA) wanted to kill two birds with one stone in the region to use Mujahedeen to ensure the retreat of Soviet from Afghanistan and exploit them as well to deter the expansion of Iranian policy. It ought to be noted that the stronger the relations between Saudi Arabia and Pakistan are, the weaker relations between Pakistan and Iran are witnessed because Pak-Iran relations are determined by the external factor of Saudi Arabia.

Moreover, Saudi-Iran relations became at the lowest ebb on the eve of execution of Nimr al-Nimr, an Iranian cleric along with 47-Shia-prisoners by Saudi Arabia (Alam, 2017). Since Saudi Arabia viewed Nimr-al-Nimr a terrorist, backed by Iran. However, Iran rejected the allegations, saying that Saudi Arabia has been involved in the massacred of Shia community in the region. On the reaction of such execution, a violent mob emerged in Iran to seize the Embassy of Saudi Arabia in Tehran which generated a war-liking situation in Iran (Banc, 2016). In this difficult time, Saudi Arabia decided to seek the help of Pakistan. No doubt, Pakistan maintained a very

careful stance over these issues (Guzansky, 2016). Moreover, the formation of 39-state- Islamic Military Counter Terrorism Coalition (IMCTC) by Saudi Arabia in November, 2015 (Bukhari, 2017), took Pak-Iran relations into surprise. Even Pakistan maintained that it would remain neutral. Moreover, the Iran was further disappointed over the designation of General Raheel Shareef, ex-Army Chief of Pakistan is the Chief Head of the said Alliance.

Pakistan, being an ethnically divided population of Sunni and Shia sects, has been much careful over the ideological differences of Saudi Arabia and Iran. Pakistan always avoided in direct involvement in the ideological conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia. The involvement of Iranian Revolutionary Guard in the process of recruitment of Shia vis-à-vis ISIS elements in Syria (McInnis, 2016) have indicated the fact Pakistan has highly vulnerable of Iran and Saudi ideological conflict.

Even the Pak-Saudi historical cooperation even gifted Pakistan with \$1.5 billion as a gift offer in 2014 (Fair, 2014). Pak-Iran relations witnessed at the lowest ebb on the eve of Pakistan's participation of the 2017-Riyadh-Summit in Saudi Arabia on May 20th, 2017 (Muzaffar, Khan, & Yaseen, 2017). Moreover, the Summit was attended by Saudi Arabian King Salman bin Abdul Aziz, US President Donald Trump and 55 Heads of states and governments from Muslim majority countries. Iran viewed the Pakistan's participation in the said Summit as Pakistan's support of Riyadh against Tehran (Muzaffar et al., 2017).

Ideological Conflict of Iran and Saudi Conflict: Impacts on Pakistan

The Sunni-Shiite schism divided the Islamic States of the world into two opposing camps where the big powers have fully exploited the situation. Iran is a Shia dominated state, leading the Shia camp while Saudi Arabia which is a Sunni dominated state, is the leader of Sunni bloc. Both Iran and Saudi Arabia have been traditional rival and have been penetrating their respective ideology in the Muslim world. Therefore, their ideological differences created room for West to further widen their gulf. Since the Islamic Revolution in 1979 in Iran, Middle East, Gulf and South Asia have witnessed sectarian violence since Iran pursued the policy of expansion of Shiaism while Saudi Arabia followed anti-Shiaism policy (Adami & Pouresmaeili, 2013). The divergence of interests between Saudi Arabia and Iran have affected entire Muslim world including Pakistan since Pakistan is the only major and atomic power among the Muslim world. Moreover, the politics of South Asia and Middle East post-9/11 period have witnessed political engineering in Afghanistan and Iran which badly complicated the politics of South Asia and Middle East. The counterproductive results of Iraq and Afghan wars dragged the regions of the Middle East and South Asia into a never-ending wars. Following the overthrow of Iraq and Afghan governments after 9/11, a political vacuum was created which were filled by dangerous non-state entities such as, Taliban, Lashkar-e-Jangvai, Al-Qaida and Islamic States of Iraq and Syria (ISIS). The clash of interest between Iran and Saudi Arabia in Middle East did not only make them the arch enemy of one another, it also paved the way for non states actors to fully utilize the ideological conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia. In addition to this, their ideological differences also complicated the socio-religious aspects of Pakistan since Pakistan has strong links with Saudi Arabia and Iran and most importantly cannot afford to disturb its relations with any of them (Behuria, 2004).

The destabilized politics of Iraq, the weak regime of Syria and Houthi advancement in Yemen created rooms for Saudi Arabia and Iran to be involved directly or indirectly in these conflicts. In addition, since the intervention of Soviet forces in Afghanistan in 1979 and outbreak of the Islamic Revolution of 1979 in Iran, the intensity of both ideologies grew considerably in the region, because it has been alleged that the governments of Saudi Arabia and Iran have been sponsoring and backing the non-state-entities respectively for the protection of their interests in Middle East (Kausch, 2017). In order to preserve the interest of Israel and deter the nuclear capability of Iran, US has been playing an important role in the region. Moreover, the US presence in Middle East, Persian Gulf and Afghanistan was meant to maintain its dominancy, to counter the proliferation of nuclear weapons of Iran and encounter terrorist activities of ISIS, Taliban and Hezbollah, however, contrary the fact that US presence in Middle East and Afghanistan has earned counterproductive results. Most importantly, the support of Pakistan to US on war on terror, has created trouble in Pak-Iran relations.

On the other hand, having historic ideological loyalty with Saudi Arabia, the Nawaz government has been much closer with Saudi Arabia, he did not only paid many official visits to Saudi Arabia, he also declared that he would support Saudi Arabia if there would be any threat to the sovereignty of Saudi Arabia (Guzansky, 2016). Such stance has tilted Pakistan towards Saudi Arabia and disturbed Pak-Iran relations. During the last tenure of Nawaz Regime, the Government of Pakistan decided to help and support Saudi Regime in Yemen, but the opposition parties, especially PPP forced the ex-Prime Minister of Pakistan, Mr. Nawaz Sharif to play a neutral role in resolving the Iran-Saudi conflict. It has to be noted that such stance of Pakistan had badly shattered the expectations of Saudi Regime, but Saudi Arabia ought to understand that Pakistan could not afford to openly side Saudi Arabia for the following reasons.

- i. Pakistan has a mixture population of Shia and Sunni, no doubt, Sunnis are in majority, still Pakistan feels that the Sunni-Shia conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia would equally disturb Pakistan.

- ii. Iran has been a close and time-tested friend of Pakistan which supported Pakistan in its difficult hours. Besides this, Iran has geographical proximity and cultural affiliation with Pakistan. Therefore, Pakistan cannot afford to disturb its relations with Iran.

Nobody can deny the fact that the ideological conflict of Saudi Arabia and Iran had always disturbed Pakistan since both countries have been close friends of Pakistan.

Historically, the sectarian activities enhanced in two folds in the region in 1979 right after outbreak of Islamic Revolution of Iran, Soviet forces intervention in Afghanistan and the siege of Mecca in Saudi Arabia. These events did not only accelerate the sectarian violence in the region, it also dragged big powers like US, USSR and Saudi Arabia into the political engineering of the region. In order to protect the Cold War interests in the region and ensure the aloofness of Iran, US equipped and trained the Mujahedeen who had fled from Afghanistan. Moreover, the proxies who were used against the Soviet forces, were later used to create sectarian violence and deter the spread of Shiaism in Afghanistan.

The Pak-US strategic partnership in 1980s did not only widen the gap between Iran and Pakistan it also strengthened the Indo-Iranian ties which was alarming for Pakistan. Feeling the impact of Indo-Iranian alliance in the region, Pakistan tried to maintain its cordial relations with Iran. Despite US and Saudi Arabian pressure, Pakistan maintained moral support for Iran during the Iran-Iraq war (1980-88) (Irfani, 1985). However, Iran and Saudi Arabia, having conflicting interest and ideological differences, created challenges for Pakistan to balance its relations between Iran and Saudi Arabia. It ought to be noted that Pakistan has always offered its good office for the mediation of the conflict of both states (Irfani, 1985).

It is disappointing to note that in order to fight ISIL with collective efforts, the regional and international powers ought to be on one page, but unfortunately, US, Saudi Arabia and Iran have different views over the end of terrorist activities in the Middle East. As a result, the terrorist activities instead of decreasing, has been accelerating seriously.

The Saudi Arabian Factor in Pak-Iran Relations

Historically, the relations between Pakistan and Iran have been extremely cordial and amicable since the birth of Pakistan. However, their relations have been affected by the external factors of US and Saudi Arabia. As a result, it has been extremely difficult for Pakistan to maintain a balanced stance over Pak-Iran-Saudi triangle. There is no denying the fact that the success of any project between Iran and Pakistan would be affected by the external factors of Saudi Arabia and US, because Saudi Arabia and the US never want Iran to be boosted economically and stabilized politically. For instance, they discouraged the Iran-Pakistan-India (IPI) gas project since they believed that such project would boost the economy of Iran (Cohen, Curtis, & Graham, 2008). It should be noted that IPI gas project was an agreement among Iran, Pakistan and India initially, however, India withdrew from the project. The conversion of IPI into IP was the need of Pakistan to get gas from Iran. However, US never wanted Iranian projects to be successful (Mazhar & Goraya, 2013). On the other hand, Iran completed the pipeline project from South Pars to Iranshahr while Pakistan has been so much slow in construction from its side due to financial insufficiency (Jalilvand, 2013). Even though Iran decided to provide a loan of \$500 million to Pakistan for the construction of the program but later refused for acute financial constraint (Yasmeen, 1994). Despite the fact that Pakistan strongly needs energy and Iran is the best option to fulfill its requirement from IP Project. But US never wants Iranian gas to be exported to other countries since US believes that such project would boost Iranian economy. No doubt, Nawaz Sharif addressed publicly on many occasions that he would complete the IP program. But he could never materialize it. As US never wants Pakistan to run any projects with Iran (Cohen et al., 2008) because Iran is the regional rival of US and Saudi Arabia. Pakistan cannot afford to upset its relations with Saudi Arabia and Iran because both are equally important for Pakistan.

Saudi Arabia has been against the Iranian gas projects for different reasons, as Saudi Arabia alleged Iran helping Syria financially. When Iran and Syria concluded a deal of 10 billion dollars for gas pipeline project from Iran to Syria through Iraq, it badly irritated Saudi Arabia. Therefore, Saudi Arabia has been trying to topple the Syrian government so that the deal would reverse. Saudi Arabia, along with US have been backing anti-Assad elements in Middle East in order to weaken the hold of Iran in Middle East. Thus, the convergence of interests between US and Saudi Arabia vis-à-vis Iran have created challenges for entire region specially and for Pakistan specifically.

On the other hand, Pakistan joined Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India (TAPI) gas project as an alternative of IP gas project (Abbas, 2012). It is generally believed that IP would boost Iran economically. It should be noted that on the withdrawal from IPI project, India received a civilian nuclear deal with US which boosted India economically and politically, but Pakistan was never offered such benefit from US since US always gives preference to India in the region. Moreover, US termed the TAPI project as the alternative of IPI which would disturb Pak-Iranian nexus. It would be better for Pakistan if it continues both gas projects simultaneously since both projects are equally important for Pakistan. In addition to this, the projects of TAPI and IP would not only end energy crisis in Pakistan, they would also create job opportunities in Pakistan. A strained relationship between Pakistan and Iran would be a negative factor for China-Pakistan-Economic-

Corridor (CPEC) since the hub of CPEC is Gwadar, Balochistan which is geographically so much close with Iran. Therefore, the Iranian factor is much important for the successful and full-fledged operation of Gwadar Port.

Policy Recommendations

The traditional rivalry and ideological differences between Saudi Arabia and Iran have not given birth to a civil war in Yemen and Syria, it has also created tough situation for Pakistan to maintain a balanced relationship vis-à-vis Iran and Saudi Arabia since Pakistan is linked with both of them ideologically, economically and politically. However, the geo-strategic convergence, identical ideology and regional common issues of Pakistan and Iran are certain areas of convergence between Pakistan and Iran which can bridge the political gap between Pakistan and Iran. Moreover, via Iran, Pakistan can suffice its energy requirement; suppress the extremism and insurgency in Balochistan since these are the common issues of both countries. More importantly, the successful materialization of Gwadar Port and full-fledged operation of CPEC are mainly depended upon the regional policies of Iran. Therefore, keeping the whole above factors, while formulating its regional policies, Pakistan has to take a great care of Iran, without harming the national interests of Saudi Arabia since Saudi Arabia is also termed to be the 2nd biggest donor of Pakistan. Most importantly, Pakistan hosts a great number of Sunni Muslim who have greater connection with Saudi Arabia. Apart from political and economic aspects, Pak-Iran shares a deep common socio-cultural heritage which binds them tightly. Therefore, Pakistan cannot afford to upset its relations with Iran and Saudi Arabia and therefore, it needs to maintain mediatory role to resolve the issues of Iran and Saudi Arabia.

Conclusion

Pakistan has cannot afford to lose its relations with Iran and Saudi Arabia since both states are equally important for Pakistan in the region. Therefore, Pakistan has been trying to play a mediatory role to settle the political and ideological conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia. Iran is one of the most important states for Pakistan due to its geographical location which does not only benefit Pakistan economically, both states can put collective efforts to end the common issues of sectarianism and terrorism. On the other hand, Saudi Arabia is also one of the important states for Pakistan since it is helped Pakistan economically and politically on many occasions. Therefore, Pakistan being the only major atomic power of Islamic world, needs to play its role to end the ideological conflict of Iran and Saudi Arabia.

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Author Information

Abdul Rab

Lasbela University
 Assistant Professor, Department of Political Studies,
 Lasbela University, Balochistan, Pakistan
 Co

Dr. Mansoor Ahmed

University of Turbat
 Pro Vice Chancellor, University of Turbat,
 Balochistan Pakistan

Muhammad Ramzan

Szabist, Karachi Campus
 Assistant Professor (Adjunct Faculty), Department of
 Social Science, Szabist, Karachi

Amir Jan

Lasbela University
 Assistant Professor, Department of Political Studies,
 Lasbela University, Balochistan, Pakistan

Mobeen Ahmed

Lasbela University
 Lecturer, Department of Sociology
 Lasbela University, Balochistan, Pakistan

Sana Ullah

Lasbela University
 Lecturer, Department of Sociology
 Lasbela University, Balochistan, Pakistan
